

Physical Education in the Brazilian Educational Law and National Curriculum Guidelines

Aline Dessupoio Chaves; Carla N. Luguetti; Michele Viviane Carbinatto

Abstract—The aim of this study was to establish the relationship between the principles of Educational Sport and the objectives of Physical Education in two Brazilian laws: National Curriculum Guidelines (PCNs) for the Elementary and Middle School Levels and the Guidelines and Basis Legislation (LDB). The method used was the survey analysis in order to determine the practices present in, or the opinions of, a specific population. The instrument used in this research was a questionnaire. After a broad review of the bibliography and according to the methodological procedures, the aim was to set the relationships between the Principles of Educational Sport and the objectives of Physical Education, according to the Brazilian Law (LDB) and National Curriculum Guidelines (PCNs) in a table made under the analysis of a group of specialists. As the relation between the principles of Educational Sport and the objectives of School Physical Education have shown, we can state that School Physical Education has gained pedagogical security for the potential use of Educational Sport as part of its contents.

Keywords—Educational Sport; Physical Education; Education

I. INTRODUCTION

THE relation between Physical Education and Sport seems to have started at the beginning of the century and has been consolidating over this period of time based on different premises at different times in History. From the 1920s and 1930s on, Sport has been gaining room inside society and, consequently, in Physical Education. The relation between School Physical Education and Sport becomes more consistent with the influence of the “Generalized Sports Method”, a French methodology disseminated in Brazil around the 1950s, which attempted to incorporate the sports contents into the methods used in Physical Education. This method represents a reaction against the old gymnastics methods, disseminated in Brazil till about 1945 [1]. The 1970s brings the importance of physical fitness under the influence of the North American Kenneth Cooper with his “Aerobic Method”, which was later adapted by Cláudio Coutinho for the preparation of the Brazilian National Football (Soccer) Team, winner of the 1970 World Cup in Mexico. The increase in importance of physical fitness and the success in football (soccer) have clearly influenced Physical Education at school, prioritizing sports practice as well as physical quality tests and measurements. Physical Education became mandatory and was included in the 1961 Guidelines and Basis Legislation (*Leis de Diretrizes e Bases*) for the elementary and middle school curricula up to the age of 18 [1]. Reporting on Physical Education from 1946 to 1968, we notice that official initiatives had a considerable decrease in PE. Nevertheless, an extensive reorganization of concepts and the ascending of the

sports phenomenon [2]. Although the French Method was preferred until the 1950s in Brazilian schools, in the post-war period a new process starts in Physical Education with the intention of a whole Education where Sport already had its own space. This new process starts with the proposal of Physical Education encompassing a bio-social and physiological concept. It is possible to notice the onset of the importance of sports games in Child Education and Physical Education geared towards “social” and educational values. Within the school universe, it is possible to observe a confusing view about what the Physical Education discipline should be or what it should be made of. This situation used to set Sport far from the educational dimension, not allowing one to understand its importance in the education of a citizen. This would justify its remaining in this context. Professionals working with Physical Education would turn the Sports-Physical Education interrelation into a perspective where both negative and positive aspects were considered.

The pedagogical practice of Physical Education has, for a long time, pointed to the confrontation between its ludic aspect and its compensating use and between its educational aspect and its purely competitive and production- and efficiency-related use, unaware of the long-standing confirmation of Sport values in the international literature.

When regarding Sport as a social phenomenon present in the entire society, it is necessary to make it clear which sports phenomenon will be approached. In this way, Sport can be manifested through three social dimensions: Education-Sports, Leisure-Sports and Performance Sports [3].

Educational Sports, referred to in social and educational principles, is a manifestation of Sport within the school setting which must be practiced by all students so that they may have the necessary educational experiences offered by Sport.

The Educational Sports issue can be conveniently understood from the Physical Education perspective, of which it can be an integrating part, since both can only be defined as to their connections with the Education process seen as a whole.

It is not sufficient, thus, to refer to, defend or consider that the essential factor in the development of the physical culture of a country is the integration of Sport to the school setting. Investigating the real meaning of this statement is crucial as well as the objective contents that are expected to circulate through a Physical Education process.

Based on these considerations, the problem lies exactly on making Educational Sport compatible with Physical Education at school. Although it may seem that this relationship exists, the issue has not yet been approached under the scientific perspective, and that motivated this research by establishing the relationship between the principles of Educational Sport and the objectives of Physical Education in the Brazilian Educational Law- Basis Legislation (LDB) and the National

Aline Dessupoio Chaves is with master-degree in Physical Education at University Castelo Branco (UCB) in 2006 (e-mail : alinedessupoio@ef.uftm.edu.br)

Curriculum Guidelines (PCNs) for the Elementary and Middle School Levels.

II. RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN EDUCATIONAL SPORT AND PHYSICAL EDUCATION IN THE SCHOOL SETTING

The Sport content to be worked with in Physical Education classes must convey a meaningless concentrated on top efficiency and competition, seeking to promote social development through cooperation preparing students to face competitions, through wins and losses. When Sport is regarded as a body culture theme and worked with under the critical-excelling method, the meaning of the values attributed to it and its regulating norms inside our social historical context are made clear. This way of organizing knowledge does not disregard the technical and tactical elements. Nevertheless, it does not regard them as the only learning contents [5]. Physical Education cannot be reduced to mechanical objectives of efficiency and performance whose sole purpose is to develop a few sports modalities favoring the fittest and ignoring the rest. In this way, classes that should be fun and relaxing become straining and oppressive, since they do not take into account pleasure, ludicity, spontaneity and the differences among the students involved. Overlooking the three social dimensions of sports, Education-Sports it is related as part of the School Physical Education, whose main aim must be directed towards citizenship with eminently educational contents. The essential values in this Sports dimension is not only the winning of the fittest but the cooperation among participants, the autonomy shown in the teacher's construction and reconstruction of knowledge, and the creativity to experience different ways of playing with friends. All in all, it involves the possibility for change, which adds to a critical and active formation of the individual. Education-Sports, is divided into Educational Sport and School Sport, both aiming at developing the sense of citizenship, the only difference being in their principles and in the objectives they add [4]. School Sport in turn is also geared towards competition and is referred to in other principles focusing on the promotion of the potential sports skills of each participant without losing sight of the formation of citizenship. In this perspective, the important is that the classes be critical and inquisitive, and that there be debates about the game rules comparing them to the social and moral rules. Thus, Education-Sport should teach the student to read, interpret and criticize the social cultural phenomenon of Sport [6]. In order to do that, the Physical Education teacher, in any Brazilian school, must be committed to developing ethical and, possibly political, values in the students. This involves the construction of a cooperative, critical and socializing learning process. One of the Education-Sport objectives must be that its participants have favorable conditions so that their psychomotor abilities be awarded with effective programs and sporting experiences, since the main aim of Sport as a social and educational factor is man. The objective of Sport, when worked with in the educational context, is the formation of the student. In this perspective, values such as cooperation, overall participation and creativity, are prioritized as opposed to the exaggerated competition, the selection of those few fit

students and the exaggerated imposition of the teacher's interests and wishes. At school, we can cite mutual responsibility, once classes are built on teacher and student help, with no room for authoritarianism and the hierarchical manifestation of power of the former over the latter. The formative aspect of Educational Sport recommends that this manifestation should not be one more reproduction of an "efficiency" sport and, for the distinction to be made, we need to dispense with the values of aspects such as selectivity, hypercompetitiveness, and favor to talent, among others. Educational Sport is understood as the sporting practices developed in the school systems and in the assystematic forms of Education, in which the social and psychological principles, such as cooperation, co-education, participation, co-responsibility and inclusion are present, and hyperactivity and selectivity are avoided, and the objectives are the education for citizenship and leisure [4]. In this way, competition is not opposed to Education. It can be present, but must be carefully orientated so that it encourages participation, stimulates cooperation and makes respect prevail among participants, avoiding attitudes of exclusion. Physical Education, in its teaching-learning process, is conditioned to the meanings attributed to it both by the current legislation and our working process established inside school and to the knowledge and conceptions of the teachers and students involved. Thus, the contents used must get the student closer to the whole of the activities, since it allows him/her to carry out an action thinking about it and based on the meaning he/she gives to it [5]. However, PE, more than all primitive physical exercises, is Education; that is, the selection and ordering of the activities to pursue its educational purposes. Educational because they lead to something that the child shall become, but still has not, and that the child shall learn, but still has not. In this way, physical exercise must complement Education through methodic principles like in the other curricular disciplines, and not only transform Physical Education into "School Sport" [7]. Nowadays, Physical Education has been continuously worked with in schools in four different manners: the Biological-Functional conception, the Formative-Recreational conception, the Technical-Sporting conception and the Critical-Emancipating conception [6]. In the Critical-Emancipating conception, the teaching of Sports in Physical Education at school must not be restricted to the development of abilities and techniques, but there must be the inclusion of theoretical and practical contents which allow the student to organize his/her participation according to his/her possibilities and necessities, seeking to achieve social and objective competence as the main objectives of teaching through autonomy acts specific to each discipline [6]. Historically, Sports in Brazil, while part of the Physical Education at school, have been understood in a limited view which many times has led the public opinion to regard it only from the Performance Sports perspective. This can be seen by the strict use of the pre-established rules of efficiency sports in search of victory as its sole purpose. At school, the role played by sport is to educate and lead the students forward in their knowledge, starting by making the means more democratic, in which everyone may practice sport, and not only the most talented. The teacher's challenge is to teach all those who

want it. And, by teaching all of those, he will accomplish the real objectives of school: to form citizens sharing the responsibility of producing knowledge with the student. The teacher, thus, must try to develop a tactic which, from a new philosophy and educational awareness of sport, allows us to face the numerous problems and hardships that currently make values such as individualism, record and performance obsession, among others, dominate and hinder the development of a democratic, creative and educational school Sport. Educators must always refer to the emancipating educational sense to the students, crossing the limits of health and the simple body domain, contributing to the plain, complete and harmonious development of the human being. Besides that, they must also favor the social growth of the participants, through a pedagogical attitude supported by action and reflection, having solidarity, cooperation, mutual respect and environmental respect and the other fundamental human values as references. In this way, Sport worked with in Physical Education must be geared towards Educational Sport, whose objectives and principles must be understood as the concern for the creation of a renewed sporting practice, adjusted and responding to the needs of an authentic formation of the student, in an educational context, renewed in itself.

III. METODOLOGY

It is a descriptive study in which the method used was the survey. This method seeks to determine the practices present in, or opinions of, a specific population. As an instrument for the study, a general table or chart was developed indicating the principles of Educational Sport against the objectives of School Physical Education according to the National Curriculum Guidelines (PCNs) [8] for the Elementary and Middle School Levels [9], the Guidelines and Basis Legislation (LDB) [1]. Ten Physical Education experts were selected and they manifested their analysis in writing. When the reformulation was suggested, the experts indicated what items should be modified. These, when considered to be recurrent and/or pertinent, were accepted after critical analysis by the author. From this analysis, the final documents were created.

IV. RESULTS

The following charts were analyzed and validated by a commission of experts with the objective to check and establish the relations between the principles of Educational Sport and the objectives of School Physical Education, according to the Brazilian Law and some renowned authors.

Table 1 shows the relationship between the principles of Educational Sport, according to Tubino et al. [4], and the objectives of School Physical Education, according to the National Curriculum Guidelines (PCNs) [8] and the Guidelines and Basis Legislation for Brazilian Education – LDB [1].

TABLE 1
 THE RELATION BETWEEN THE PRINCIPLES OF EDUCATIONAL SPORT AND THE OBJECTIVES OF SCHOOL PHYSICAL EDUCATION ACCORDING TO THE NATIONAL LEGISLATION

PRINCIPLES OF EDUCATIONAL SPORT (TUBINO et al., 2007) [4]	NATIONAL CURRICULUM GUIDELINES FOR ELEMENTARY AND MIDDLE SCHOOLS (PCNs) [9]	GUIDELINES AND BASIS LEGISLATION FOR BRAZILIAN EDUCATION (LDB) [1]
1) PARTICIPATION Allow all students to participate in sporting practices, including the adjustment of rules so that everyone can take part in the educational and sporting activities. When integrating the group of fans, the imaginary of a club or team passion, the person is also inserted in the principle of participation.	1.1) Place oneself in a critical, responsible and constructive manner in the different social situations, using dialogue as a means to mediate conflicts and making group decisions which can be suggested by the students under the supervision of the teachers. 1.2) Use the different kinds of language: verbal, musical, mathematical, graphic, plastic and body language – as a means to produce, express and communicate its ideas, interpret and enjoy the cultural productions in public and private contexts, meeting different situations and intentions of communication.	1.1.1) Freedom to learn, teach, investigate and disseminate culture, thought and knowledge, not restricted solely to the sporting practice but also containing theoretical elements such as sport background and its relationship with culture. 1.1.2) Establish the link between school education, work and social practices, also emphasizing the situation of participation as to the professionals linked to the sports field.
2) INCLUSION Include the participation of those with special needs, taking into account the fact that sport may be a convergence point among cultures, i.e., establish interfaces among the several regional aspects of the Brazilian culture.	2.1) Know the basic characteristics of Brazil in the social, material and cultural spheres as a means to progressively build the notion of national identity and the feeling of belonging to the country, valuing the individuality of the people.	2.2.1) Pluralism of ideas and pedagogical conceptions.

	2.2) Develop self-knowledge and the feeling of confidence in one's affection, physical, cognitive, ethic and aesthetic capacities, as well as of personal relation and social inclusion, in order to act with perseverance in search of knowledge and the exertion of citizenship.	2.2.2) Free public school teaching in official establishments, with a main focus on quality.	life.	valuing and adopting healthy eating habits and doing physical activities as one of the basic aspects of quality life and act with responsibility in relation to one's health and the <u>group's health</u> ;
3) CO-EDUCATION Keep only the natural biological differences as reference in the sports practice, integrating heterogeneous situations of gender, age, social and economic level, physical conditions, and others.	3.1) Know and value the plurality of the Brazilian social and cultural history, as well as the social and cultural aspects of other peoples and nations, placing oneself against any kind of discrimination on the basis of cultural differences, social classes, beliefs, gender, ethnical groups and other individual and social characteristics.	3.3.1) Value, stimulate and provide extra-curricular activities. 3.3.2) Establish the link between school education, work and social practices.		5.4) Question reality by formulating problems and trying to solve them, using logical thinking, creativity, intuition, the capacity for critical analysis, selecting procedures and checking its appropriateness.
4) COOPERATION Promote joint actions for the achievement of common objectives during sports practices such as seeing winning as a group conquest.	4.1) Understand citizenship as social and political participation, as well as the exertion of political, civil and social rights and duties, adopting daily attitudes of solidarity, cooperation and repudiation to injustice, respecting the other and demanding the same respect for oneself.	4.4.1) Equality of conditions of access and permanence in school regardless of ethnical group, social and economic background. 4.4.2) Respect to freedom and care for tolerance.		
5) CO-RESPONSIBILITY Provide the young participant with the co-responsibility not only in decision-making processes, such as adjustment to rules, organizational measures, etc, but also in performing the school project established in the daily	5.1) See oneself as an integrating and acting transformer of the environment, identifying its elements and their interactions, contributing actively to the improvement of the environment; 5.2) Know our own body and care for it,	5.5.1) Democratic management of the public school system, based on this Law and on the legislation of the school systems.		

Thus, we can observe that there is a clear relationship between Educational Sport and the objectives worked with in the School Physical Education, which shows the importance of using Educational Sport in its principles such as the contents in the Physical Education classes at school.

V. CONCLUSION

According to the course of this study and from the final documents, as a result of the investigation on the principles of Educational Sport and the objectives of Physical Education at school, we could see that there is a relationship between them which has not yet been validated in the scientific community.

According to the bibliographical review of this study, and from its main objective, the scientific purposes and the investigated questions, we could see that Educational Sport can be used as contents of Physical Education at school, based on the relation between the principles of Educational Sport and the objectives of School Physical Education.

From these relations, it was possible to observe that in practice they do not occur in Physical Education classes, where there still prevail the principles of efficiency sport. Thus, when Sport shall be worked with as part of the school's contents, we should prioritize the educational values found in the principles of Educational Sport, which are closely related to the objectives of Physical Education at school established by the Brazilian Legislation (*LDB* and *PCNs*) [1,8]

It is therefore recommended that the documents generated in this dissertation be assessed and disseminated among Physical Education professionals who work with the intent of educating and forming citizens who are aware of the educational values.

It is also recommended that more studies be carried out about this theme so that the principles of Educational Sport, such as participation, inclusion, co-education, cooperation and co-responsibility, be increasingly present in the Physical Education classes so that Sport, while seen as a school content, be worked with in a real educational manner.

As the relation between the principles of Educational Sport and the objectives of School Physical Education have shown, we can state that School Physical Education has gained pedagogical security for the potential use of Educational Sport as part of its contents.

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Michele Viviene Carbinatto, is PhD student from University of São Paulo (USP). Graduated in Physical Education at State University of Campinas (UNICAMP) in 2003. Her master-degree in Physical Education and Corporeity was finished in 2006 at Metodista University of Piracicaba (UNIMEP). Since 2010 she became a Professor of the Sports Science Department at Federal University of Triangulo Mineiro (UFTM). She has been working with researches about teacher/ coach education and gymnastics for all. Contact: mcarbinatto@ef.uftm.edu.br

Aline Dessupoio Chaves, is master-dregree in Physical Education at University Castelo Branco (UCB) in 2006. Graduated in Physical Education at Federal University of Juiz de Fora (UFJF) in 2001. Since 2009 she became a Professor of the Sports Science Department at Federal University of Triangulo Mineiro (UFTM). She has been working with researches about aquatic activities and talent sport. Contact: alinedessupoio@ef.uftm.edu.br

Carla Nascimento Luguetti, is master-dregree in Physical Education at University of São Paulo (USP) in 2010. Graduated in Physical Education at University Santa Cecília (UNISANTA) in 2001. Since 2007 she became a Professor of the Physical Education Department at University Santa Cecília (UNISANTA). She has been working with researches training youth, sport pedagogy, growth and development. Contact: luguetti@usp.br